

Preparation and characterization of cationic soap-washing agent and its working mechanism for the removal of unfixed dyes for reactive dyed cotton fabrics

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Abstract: Reactive dyes have better properties in terms of color fastness and are mostly used for the coloration of cotton fabric. However, reactive dyes always tend to be hydrolyzed during the dyeing process and approximately 1/4th gets hydrolyzed which is responsible for decreasing the color fastness of the finished fabric. This hydrolyzed dye adheres to the substrate and keeps on getting removed during washing treatments causing poor wash fastness. So, after dyeing is completed, an effective wash should be carried out by using an appropriate soap-washing agent to remove those additional unfixed dyes in order to get the best washing efficiency. Thus, the soap-washing agents play a significant role in the removal of unfixed dyes as well as increase overall washing efficiency. Hence, in this article, our aim is to develop effective cationic soap-washing agents through the copolymerization of N-vinylpyrrolidone with N-vinyl imidazole. All the samples were washed by using different soap-washing agents for 30 minutes under 90°C temperatures. It was found that the unfixed dye removal efficiencies were influenced by the pH factor and the concentration of soap-washing agents. The best soap-washing result was obtained for VP/VI20(80%/20%) soap-washing agent pH 10 in liquors for 1g/L and the characteristics were analyzed by Data color650 spectrophotometer, UV-visible spectrophotometer, Dry and wet rubbing fastness, and Fourier transform infrared (FTIR).

Keywords: Reactive dye, Soap-washing agent, Color strength(k/s), Residual dye molecules.

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I. Introduction

Dyeing is one of the most important parameters in textile industries around the world and for various colorations on fabric different types of dyes are used [1]. Among different dyes, Reactive dyes are mostly used for the coloration of cotton fabric and always have had a significant place in dyeing industries over the last few decades [2]. Reactive dyes are a highly successful class of modern synthetic dyes. Demand for reactive dyes is increasing daily because of their lower production cost, Excellent wet color fastness, bright color, and facile application process [3]. Reactive dyes offer excellent colorfastness properties when dyed on cotton, silk, wool, and regenerated cellulose fibers [4]. During the reactive dyeing process, the reactive dye molecules continually tend to be hydrolyzed, and figure 1.1 shows the reaction with cotton fiber and water. However, hydrolyzed/unfixed dyes are generated and fail to react with fibers, which are responsible for decreasing colorfastness and creating undesirable color migration among fabrics during washing [4]. If those unfixed dyes are not removed properly, it will affect the color and wash fastness and create undesirable effects on the fabrics. Hence, after dyeing is finished, effective soap-washing should be carried out to remove unfixed dyes in terms of excellent washing performance [5]. Thus, the soap-washing agent plays a significant role during washing in removing unfixed dyes and preventing attaching those unfixed dyes molecules among fabrics. Conventionally, to obtain excellent colorfastness properties, after dyeing is finished, the unfixed dye substance is neutralized throughout the multiple washing and soaping process for removing those unfixed dyes as much as possible, which is also water time and energy-consuming as well as the costly process [6].

Figure 1.1: Reaction of a reactive dye with cotton fiber and water.

Currently, it is found that polymers are mostly used for the washing process that is shown in figure 1.2. The polymer-dye binding formation conducted throughout the interaction between polymer and dye demonstrated many attractive, interesting and significant practical characteristics. Some special factors such as hydrophobic, Coulombic, and steric connections are mainly responsible for thermochemical and dynamic complex formation[7]. Poly(vinylpyrrolidone), PVP is a highly water-soluble nonionic, non-toxic, chemically stable polymer that can complex hydrophilic and hydrophobic substances[8]. Because of those outstanding characteristics, PVP has an extensive range of applications such as the removal of hydrolyzed dyes, dye transfer inhibitors, binders, soaps, and detergents in the textile industry [9]. Poly (N-vinyl imidazole), NVI is a water-soluble cationic polymer with special characteristics such as electrical conductivity, pH-dependent, and metal ions binding[8]. The imidazole group plays a significant role in dye-binding through electrostatic attraction between polymer and dye [10]. In this article, we mainly focus on the following issues such as ① removing unfixed/hydrolyzed dyes, ② Increase washing efficiency, ③ Improve color fastness properties.

Figure 1.2: Chemical structure of polymers.

II. Experimental method and Materials

2.1 Experimental drugs

In this article, Pure cotton fabric was supplied by Zhejiang Kefeng Silicone Co., Ltd. and applied without any treatment. N-Vinylpyrrolidone (NVP), N-Vinyl Imidazole (NVI), Hydrogen peroxide (25% H₂O₂), Hydrochloric acid (HCL), Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH), Ammonia solution (NH₃. H₂O), the above are all analytical pure chemicals were supplied by Hangzhou Gaojing Fine Chemical Industry Co., Ltd and was used directly without any furthermore purification.

2.2 Soap-Washing Agent's Preparation and Method of Washing

2.2.1 Synthesis of Copolymers P(VP-co-VI)

All the soap-washing agents are prepared through the copolymerization of NVP with NVI (VP-co-VI) in an aqueous solution that contains 38% chemicals. First, chemicals were measured into a beaker and mixed with water by stirring with a glass rod. Then adjust the pH in solution around 8-9 by adding ammonia (NH₃. H₂O) solution. After that, the mixer of chemicals was poured into a three-neck round bottom flask and run the experiment around 5-6 hours under 74-75°C temperature. During the copolymerization process, hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) was used as the initiator and was added while the temperature was around 62°C. The weight of H₂O₂ was 1.14g (3% of 38g) for all the soap-washing agents.

2.2.2 Method of Soap-washing

Using developed soap-washing agents, the fabric that has been dyed with reactive dyes was used for the soap-washing process. During washing, a white cotton fabric was used as a sample to analyze the soaping efficiency.

Soap-washing formula: Soaping agent	0.5g/L, 1.0g/L
Liquor ratio	1:10~25
pH value	4(acidic),7(neutral),10(alkaline)
Duration	30min X 90°C

2.2.3 Mechanism of Soap-washing Agents

2.3 Characteristics Analysis

2.3.1 Color Migration Analysis

The color strength (K/S) of the washed fabric was calculated by using data color650 spectrophotometer from the Kubelka-Munk equation as given below (Eq. I). where the absorption coefficient of the substrate is K, S is determining the scattering coefficient of the substrate, and R is the reflectance of the dyed fabric at λ_{max} . After folding each fabric twice, measurements were taken at three different positions on the fabric surface [11].

$$K/S = \frac{(1-R)^2}{2R} \dots \dots \dots (I)$$

2.3.2 Rubbing Fastness Analysis

This process examines the amount of color shifted from one surface to another surface during rubbing. Using the AATCC crock meter, the test is performed according to the AATCC testing procedure. The test specimen was graded using a visual greyscale for both dry and wet rubbing fastness, and the grades of rubbing fastness are mentioned as 5, excellent; 4, good; 3, fair; 2, poor; and 1, extremely poor. To investigate the dry and wet rubbing, White samples are cut into (5cm x 5cm) square shape and rubbed approximately 20 times in 10 seconds while the finger of the tester carrying a weight of 2-6 N with the contact of the test sample. A separate sample is used for the dry and weight rubbing test. The wet rubbing test was done by using a wet sample that water content is up to 95% to 105%. All the tests are conducted under the atmospheric conditions of $20 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $65 \pm 5\% \text{ RH}$ [12].

2.3.3 Residual Dye Concentration in Washing Liquors

After washing was completed, Dye concentration in washing liquors was measured by using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (UV mini-1240) according to the “Beer-Lambert” law shown in equation II, and it is known to all that the absorbance is directly proportional to the concentration of dye in solution [13].

$$A = \epsilon cl \dots \dots \dots (II)$$

Where A indicates the absorbance, c determines the concentration mol⁻¹, and l is pathlength in cm and molar extinction coefficient.

2.3.4 Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

According to the standard method, the Nicolet 5700 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer (American Thermoelectric Company) was used for Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy analysis.

III. Results and Discussion

3.1 Color Migration and Colorfastness Analysis (PVP vs Water)

At the end of the dyeing, the unfixed dyes existed mainly inner and on the surface of the cotton fiber via Van Der Waals force between dye and fiber or between dye and dye[3]. In the initial stage, the dyed fabric was washed with PVP for 1g/L and only with water to analyze the unfixed dye removal efficiency, and the results are shown in Figure 3.1. From Figure 3.1(a), the unfixed dye removal efficiency for PVP is higher than only water washed.

Figure 3.1: a) Color strength (k/s) of washed fabric (PVP vs Water), b) dry, and c) wet Colorfastness properties of the dyed fabric after washing (PVP vs Water).

After washing, both the dry and wet colorfastness were analyzed, and the results are shown in Figure 3.1(b, c). From the results, the unfixed dye removal efficiency of PVP is better than only washing with water. From Figure 3.1 results, it is clear that the PVP polymer is not efficient for removing unfixed dye as PVP is a nonionic polymer though it is

highly soluble in water^[9]. During washing, polymer dye complexation cannot occur through electrostatic attraction because of the nonionic nature of PVP in washing liquors. As a result, dye molecules have a high affinity to stay in the water and are attached to the new fabric, which creates stains to the new fabric and causes poor colorfastness.

3.2 A series of VP/VI Soap-washing Agents

Cotton fabric contains an anionic charge on its surface in an aqueous solution, So the effective soap-washing agent should have cationic characteristics ^[14]. Because the hydroxyl group is present in soap-washing agents bearing positive charges and both can interact with each other through electrostatic dipolar and produce hydrogen bonds in washing liquors. As polyvinyl pyrrolidone is not efficient for removing unfixed dye, we added a cationic monomer N-vinyl imidazole, and the soap-washing agents are prepared through copolymerization with copolymerization N-vinyl pyrrolidone. Recently, it has been found that the use of polymer for washing processes increased rapidly in textile industries because polymer plays a significant role in removing unfixed dyes from reactive dyed cotton fabric^[15]. Theoretically, the color strength of the washed fabrics should be decreased with the increase of unfixed dyes removal ^[16]. Among different ratios of NVP and NVI, the most effective one is VP/VI20 for removing unfixed dyes at pH 10 in washing liquors through wash-off for 1g/L, and the color strength(k/s) results are shown in figures 3.2 (a, b) both for 0.5g/L and 1g/L. This indicates that VI in VP/VI20(80%/20%) soap-washing agent influences the removal of the unfixed dye, and the decrease of VI leads to higher color strength(k/s) value which means less unfixed dyes removal. According to the unfixed dyes removal efficiency, the sequences of different soap-washing agents are VP/VI20(80%/20%)> VP/VI15(85%/15%)> VP/VI25(75%/25%)> VP/VI10(90%/10%)> VP/VI30(70%/30%).

Figure 3.2: Color strength (k/s) of washed fabric after being washed with different soap-washing agents both for a) 0.5g/L and b) 1g/L.

At alkaline conditions, more OH⁻ ions will help interact with cationic soap-washing agents and anionic unfixed reactive dyes molecules through electrostatic, dipolar, and hydrogen bonding. Mostly electrostatic attraction between anionic dyes and the cationic soap-washing agent is responsible for removing unfixed dyes. However, it is also found that the concentration of soap-washing agents and the pH value in washing liquors greatly affect the dyes removal efficiencies. The reactive dyed cotton fabric can't wash at low pH as the dyeing process was done in alkaline conditions. So, washing the dyed fabric at low pH is expensive because it needs acid in washing liquors. We have shown the results for different pH in liquors to analyze the effect of pH for the removal of unfixed dyes during washing, and the best result was obtained at pH 10 in washing liquors.

3.3 Color Migration and Colorfastness Analysis (PVP vs VP/VI20)

Once we found that VP/VI20(80%/20%) soap-washing has excellent unfixed dyes removal efficiency and excellent color fastness properties, we compared washing efficiency between PVP and VP/VI20(80%/20%) to prove that VP/VI20(80%/20%) soap-washing was highly effective. According to the color strength(k/s) results from figure 3.3(a),

after analyzing unfixed dyes removal efficiency, VP/VI20(80%/20%) is more effective than washing with only PVP. So, incorporating cationic VI for a soap-washing agent was workable for removing unfixed dyes^[8]. This indicates that the addition of VI, a soap-washing agent, can form electrolyte complexation through electrostatic interaction between dye molecules and fabric or dye to dye with a high affinity towards fabric and re-stains on the fabric^[17]. This is believed that the favorable binding process is mainly related to two important factors hydrophobic and electrostatic interaction. The results suggested that the hydrophobic interaction between polymer and dye plays a significant role in the polymer-dye binding process, and the binding capacity of PVI is primarily dependent on its charges. The binding force between anionic day and polycation is also influenced by coulombic interactions^[18]. From figures 3.3(c, d), it can also be seen that both the dry and wet rubbing fastness is quite good than PVP after washed with VP/VI20(80%/20%) soap-washing agent and also have lower residual dye concentration in liquors after washing that is shown in figure 3.3(b). So, it can be concluded that carbonyl, hydroxyl groups of VPs, amino-functional group, an imidazole ring in VI are highly workable for removing unfixed dyes through the wash-off process.

Figure 3.3: a) Color strength(k/s) strength washed fabric, b) Residual dye concentration, c) dry, and d) wet rubbing fastness comparison between PVP vs VP/VI20.

3.4 FTIR Analysis

The FTIR spectra for pure PVP and copolymers of P(VP-co-VI) are shown in figure 3.4, indicating that we have successfully synthesized of copolymers. In Figures 3.4 (a), the peaks are at 1652 cm^{-1} with the strong intensity corresponding to amide(I) and corresponding to the C=O and C-N groups. The pick shows a broad bending stretch of 3446 cm^{-1} , indicating that PVP contains absorbed water (O-H). The peaks at 1423 cm^{-1} and 1287 cm^{-1} show the bending stretch of the (C-N=O) and (C=O) groups. The peak located at 2955 cm^{-1} in Figure 3.4(a) shows the stretching vibration of (C-H) of PVP, and the peak located at 2360 cm^{-1} shows the stretching vibration of P-H^[9,19]. From figure 3.4(b), the FTIR spectra indicate that the height of peaks increased with the increase of VI, and the spectrum of poly (VP-co-VI) with characteristic peaks appeared at 3105 cm^{-1} and 2338 cm^{-1} shows the stretching vibrations of imidazole ring, C=C-H/N=C-H^[10]. The peak at 1691 cm^{-1} also shows the stretching vibration of (C-C/N-C), while the peak located at 2916 cm^{-1} shows the bending

stretch of C-H. These data confirmed that the poly (VP-co-VI) copolymer beads were formed with functional groups VI^[20,21] and successfully done the synthesis through copolymerization.

Figure 3.4: FTIR spectra of pure a) PVP and b) P(VP-co-VI).

IV. Conclusion

This article mainly focuses on the development of cationic soap-washing agent for reactive dyed cotton fabrics as reactive dye contain anionic sulphonate group. It was found that the prepared soap-washing agent through the copolymerization of NVP with NVI is highly effective for the removal of unfixed dyes during washing process. Among different chemical ratios, the best washing results was obtained for VP/VI20(80%/20%) at pH 10 in washing liquors for 1g/L concentration. After washing with VP/VI20(80%/20%) soap-washing agent, the colorfastness was increased from 1 to 5 and the white cotton fabric that was used as a sample almost remain unchanged which also indicate that the developed VP/VI20(80%/20%) soap-washing agent able to prevent color migration during wash-off. So, it can be concluded that the developed VP/VI20(80%/20%) soap-washing agent is not only effective for the removal of unfixed dyes, but also increase overall colorfastness properties of the finished fabrics along with facile industrial application.

V. References

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